

MANAGEMENT TASKS AND CHALLENGES OF ENTREPRENEURSHIP EDUCATION FOR SUSTAINABILITY OF UNIVERSITIES IN IMO STATE, NIGERIA

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Abstract:

The study examined management tasks and challenges of entrepreneurship education for sustainability of universities in Imo State, Nigeria. The study adopted descriptive survey research design. The population and sample of the study was made up of 90 directors, non-teaching staff and lecturers of entrepreneurship education in universities in Imo State. A researcher-made rating scale titled "Management Tasks and Challenges of Entrepreneurship Education for Sustainability of Universities Scale" (MTCEESUS) with 20 items was used for data collection. The instrument was validated by specialists in Educational Management and Educational Measurement and Evaluation. Cronbach alpha statistics was used for the reliability of the instrument which obtained an index of 0.85. Mean and standard deviation were used to answer the research questions and hypotheses were tested using one sample t-test at 0.05 level of significance. Findings showed that entrepreneurship education directors are doing their tasks in the management of entrepreneurship education for sustainability of universities in Imo State, Nigeria. However, some challenges are facing the management of entrepreneurship education for sustainability of universities in the state. The study further recommended that: the state and federal government should endeavour to provide adequate fund for the administration of entrepreneurship education in universities in Imo State.

Keywords: management tasks, challenges, entrepreneurship education and sustainability

1. Introduction

Today, sustainability is one of the creditable topics all over the world. The need to maintain and sustain quality gave rise to sustainability. Sustainability is construct, which envision development as meeting the need of the present generation without

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compromising the needs of the future generation. It implied that while education meets the need of the present, it does not compromise the ability of the future generations to meet their own needs. Nevertheless, this ability to meet the needs is determined by human capital (through education, technology advancement) and through physical capital (machine, tool and so on). Sustainability is one, which takes into account the well-being of future generations in the present national development policies, priorities, planning and consumption patterns (Ugoh, 2008). It is a behaviour that can sustain indefinitely into the future. One of the strategies of realizing sustainability in Nigeria is through education.

Education generally, is a social process that helps to maintain a dynamic society since the creation of human beings. It is through education that the cultural heritages are transferred from generation to generation. Formally, the business of education is carried out through three major levels, viz: primary, secondary and tertiary. Tertiary institutions of learning comprise all higher institutions such as colleges of education, polytechnics and universities. The universities are vested with the responsibility of providing skilled and high-level workforce for the economy (Oyeniyi, 2011). The Federal Republic of Nigeria (2013), stated that university education shall make optimum contribution to national development by:

- a. Intensifying and diversifying its programmes for the development of high-level manpower within the context of the needs of the nation;
- b. Making professional course contents reflect our national requirements;
- c. Making all students part of a general programme of all-round improvement in university education, to offer general study courses such as history of ideas, philosophy of knowledge, nationalism, and information technology (IT); and
- d. Making entrepreneurial skills acquisition a requirement for all Nigerian universities (p.41).

The realization of the fourth objective places entrepreneurship education at the center and the rationale behind the objectives could be linked to the inability of graduates to stand on their own and be self-employed after school. This could also be seen in the high rate of unemployment among university graduates. Unemployment and unemployable graduates have become a serious challenge to university educators and the Nigerian government. Adegbenjo (2012) was of the view that this phenomenon constituted a waste of resources in the manpower development of this nation. The author further stated that the type of education that is needed for self-employment and national development has changed to include general reasoning, creative problem solving and behavioural skills as well as positive cognitive styles as against the narrow cognitive and occupational skills sought in more directed work environment. This need explains why the Nigerian government stipulated in the national policy on education, the acquisition of appropriate skills, abilities and competencies, both mental and physical, as a prerequisite for the individual to live in and contribute to the development of the society (FRN, 2013).

Entrepreneurship Education (EEd) according to Onu (2006) is the type of education which provides learners with the basic knowledge, skills, attitude, and ideas for self-reliance. In other words, entrepreneurship education through the inculcation of entrepreneurial skills, should make recipients proficient in career related areas and so launch them into the business world with a view to overcoming the problem of unemployment and over-dependency on white-collar jobs. Akunnaya (2012) defined entrepreneurship skills as those skills that will enable the individual to maximize the resources around him within the limits of his capabilities. If the ability of individuals to utilize resources around them is tied to their capacity, there is a need to build and enhance capacity towards resource utilization for job and wealth creation. Entrepreneurship education is an inevitable tool for this capacity building. There is need to match resource utilization with appropriate knowledge through entrepreneurship education. Entrepreneurship education can be used for wealth creation, poverty reduction, ensuring social-economic empowerment, sustained self and national development.

It is imperative to state that effective administration is indispensable for the successful functioning of any programme in any institution (Entrepreneurship education inclusive). Without effective and meaningful administration, it will be impossible to deliver results. Entrepreneurship administrative tasks are those entrepreneurship management strategies which include planning, organizing, staffing, directing, reporting and coordinating which an administrator uses to achieve the objective of entrepreneurship education. Agreeing with the above statement, Ezeani (2012) states that entrepreneurship administrative task strategies are those management techniques which the university administrators employ to lead the school to a greater heights through the acquisition of required skills which help students to be self-employed and self-reliant after graduation.

In administration of entrepreneurship education, the directors must ensure that they plan, organize, direct and coordinate the activities of human resources for the training of students. This will help in the acquisition of entrepreneurial skills by providing training centers and articulating the programmes to help explore different opportunities (Oku, Ejiogu and Agim, 2012). To realize this, the directors of entrepreneurship education of universities are saddled with the administrative tasks of personnel management, material resource management and fund management.

The entrepreneurship directors of state and federal university must ensure that funds are sourced, provided and managed judiciously. No educational programme can survive without adequate funding. The issues of funding and management of available ones in entrepreneurship education need to be stressed for optimal realization of the objectives of the programme. In the aspect of managing the material resources, the school directors must ensure that the equipment/facilities are provided and managed, to enable a skillful teacher to achieve a level of instructional effectiveness that far exceeds what is possible when they are not there. Material resources are those facilities that help in promoting teaching and learning in any institution. In line with the above statement,

Emetaron (2004) asserted that one of the indices for measuring quality education programme for sustainability is the facilities available in the institution.

According to Onu (2013), to effectively promote entrepreneurship in state and federal tertiary institutions in Nigeria, school administrators play a vital role as lecturers/teachers' competence must be carefully assessed by them. Lecturers/teachers, as important role models, must possess requisite knowledge of entrepreneurship to be able to motivate students in developing a positive attitude toward entrepreneurship (Oku, 2012). Focusing on entrepreneurship in teacher training and providing courses in competence development to working teachers are critically important. Human development is a vital vehicle in the realization of entrepreneurship education objectives. Of all the resources at the disposal of any institution, the teacher is the most important. This is because the teacher harnesses and coordinates the various financial and material resources (Achunine, 2007). The administrator should ensure that they train and retrain the lecturers through quality development programmes like orientation programmes, workshops and conferences so that the lecturers will meet up with the challenges in the teaching of entrepreneurship education.

In spite of the crucial role of entrepreneurship education in equipping the individual with skills to be independent and productive, there are lots of challenges still confronting the implementation of entrepreneurship education curriculum in Nigerian universities. Some of these challenges include: poor funding, lack of training facilities, inadequate manpower, inadequate time allotted to the teaching of the subject, poor curriculum content, lack of practical training and lack of practical time (Ifedili and Ofoegbu, 2011). Besides, the style of teaching of entrepreneurship education across the tertiary institutions in Nigeria has been flawed because of too much emphasis on the theoretical aspects and the absence of standard textbooks and other useful learning materials on entrepreneurship education. Most of the available textbooks according to Onye and Anyaogu (2014) are deficient and do not address the peculiar nature of the Nigerian business environment. This view was buttressed by Garba (2004) when he observed that the goals of entrepreneurship education in Nigeria have become elusive due to poor curriculum implementation across tertiary institutions. This affected the idea of development as most tertiary institutions have inadequate fund and the required resources to teach entrepreneurship education, leading to non-realization of the objectives of entrepreneurship education.

Gabadeen and Raimi (2012) found that there is inadequate funding of entrepreneurship education, which has negatively affected the implementation of entrepreneurship education curricula, a fact attested to by National Universities Commission (NUC) and National Board for Technical Education (NBTE). In addition, Gabadeen and Raimi (2012) found out that there is overemphasis on theoretical training due to lack of time for practical training. Entrepreneurship education is better imparted through industrial tours, professional talks from successful business owners and real execution of business projects while in schools. Presently, the focus is more on theoretical instructions and mentoring. Finally, it is pertinent to note that Nigerian universities do

not have adequate and high level manpower for effective teaching and learning of entrepreneurship education in the country. The available teachers were drafted from the existing faculties and have not acquired additional skills to cope with the challenges of the new curriculum. One of the major challenges now confronting entrepreneurship education in Nigeria as revealed by Ediagbonya (2013) is identifying and recruiting the qualified teachers who have the appropriate knowledge and pedagogy to impart entrepreneurial skills and competences on the students.

Empirically, Asiyai (2009) found the roles of school administrators in effective management of entrepreneurship education to include provision of training on entrepreneurship education for teachers. Also Uche and Adesope (2009) findings revealed that workshops and seminars are to be conducted for all faculties and at Academic Staff Union of Universities (ASUU) level to expose the lecturers to the concept of entrepreneurship and what their roles are in the implementation of entrepreneurship education in the university. Asiyai (2009) further revealed the roles of school administrators in effective management of entrepreneurship education to include soliciting for improved funding of the programme through collaboration with Non Governmental Organizations (NGOs), Community Based Organizations (CBOs), and external agencies, improved monitoring and evaluation of the programme.

However, Onye and Anyaogu (2014) revealed that: inadequate provision of funds for entrepreneurial research, lack of fund to carry out practical works for students, inadequate funds to carry out day to day entrepreneurship activities and inadequate budgetary provisions challenges the implementation of the programme. Similarly, Obioma (2014) found among others that the level of funding entrepreneurship education curriculum in Universities located in Imo State is too low, and this hinders the realization of its objectives. Also, Anaele, Adelokun, Dem and Barfa (2014) found out that poor state of infrastructure poses challenge to entrepreneurship education in Nigerian schools. Also, Onye and Anyaogu (2014) found out that lack of teaching staff poses a challenge to the implementation of the programme. Congruently, Oku (2012) study identified that inadequate number of lecturers to teach entrepreneurship education in terms of quantity and quality is among some of the challenges facing the effective management of entrepreneurship education in Nigerian universities. The above findings led the present researcher to ask that: what are the management tasks and challenges of entrepreneurship education for sustainability of universities in Imo State, Nigeria? This is the thrust of this study.

The general purpose of this study was to examine management tasks and challenges of entrepreneurship education for sustainability of universities in Imo State, Nigeria. Specifically, the study sought to ascertain:

1. the management tasks of entrepreneurship education for sustainability of universities in Imo State, Nigeria, and
2. the management challenges of entrepreneurship education for sustainability of universities in Imo State, Nigeria.

The following research questions guided the study.

1. What are the management tasks of entrepreneurship education for sustainability of universities in Imo State, Nigeria?
2. What are the management challenges of entrepreneurship education for sustainability of universities in Imo State?

The following null hypotheses were formulated to guide the study and they were tested at significant level of $P < 0.05$.

HO₁: The mean score of lecturers in management tasks of entrepreneurship education for sustainability of universities in Imo State, Nigeria is not significantly greater than 25.

HO₂: The mean score of lecturers in managing challenges of entrepreneurship education for sustainability of universities in Imo State, Nigeria is not significantly greater than 25.

2. Methodology

This study adopted the descriptive survey research design. The population and sample of the study was made up of 90 directors, non-teaching staff and lecturers of entrepreneurship education in universities in Imo State. A researcher-made rating scale titled "Management Tasks and Challenges of Entrepreneurship Education for Sustainability of Universities Scale" (MTCEESUS) with 20 items was used for data collection. The instrument was duly validated by two specialists in Educational Management and one in Educational Measurement and Evaluation. Cronbach alpha statistic was used for the reliability of the instrument which obtained an index of 0.85. In analyzing the data for the study, mean and standard deviation were used to answer the research questions, while the hypotheses were tested using one sample t-test at 0.05 level of significance.

3. Results

Table 1: Management Tasks of Entrepreneurship Education
for Sustainability of Universities in Imo State, Nigeria

S/N	Item Statement: The director and management of entrepreneurship education;	n	$\bar{X}$	S	Remark
1	Assign qualified lecturers for the teaching of various entrepreneurship education courses	90	3.74	.56	Agreed
2	Provide orientation programmes for lecturers to create awareness on the need for entrepreneurship education	90	3.44	.60	Agreed
3	Ensure that entrepreneurship centres are equipped to NUC standard.	90	2.44	.72	Disagreed
4	Source for special intervention funds	90	2.47	.52	Disagreed
5	Involve venture capitalists in the funding of the centre	90	2.48	.61	Disagreed
6	Ensure that modern information technology facilities for information gathering and dissemination are provided	90	3.35	.66	Agreed

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7	Ensure that programmes are well articulated to help students explore different possibilities.	90	3.52	.63	Agreed
8	Identify and assign lecturers in areas of need.	90	3.47	.72	Agreed
9	Assign qualified lecturers for the teaching of various courses.	90	3.40	.69	Agreed
10	Ensure that special intervention funds are sourced for	90	2.31	.70	Disagreed
Cluster Mean			29.72		
Mean of Item Means			2.972		

A look at table 1 shows the mean response of lecturers on management tasks of entrepreneurship education for sustainability of universities in Imo State, Nigeria. The result revealed that all the items, except items 3, 4, 5 and 10 were considered as agreed having recorded mean scores above the criterion mean of 2.50. A look at the standard deviations proved that they are far away from the mean and also that scores in the distribution are close to each other. It was also indicated that the mean of item mean is 2.972 showing that the entrepreneurship education directors are doing their tasks in the management of entrepreneurship education for sustainability of universities in Imo State, Nigeria. Some of the task areas they are performing are in assigning qualified lecturers for the teaching of various entrepreneurship education courses, providing orientation programmes for lecturers to create awareness on the need for entrepreneurship education, ensuring that modern information technology facilities for information gathering and dissemination are provided and ensuring that programmes are well articulated to help students explore different possibilities.

Table 2: Management Challenges of Entrepreneurship Education
for Sustainability of Universities in Imo State, Nigeria

S/N	Item Statement: The director and management of entrepreneurship education are faced with the following challenges;	n	$\bar{X}$	S	Remark
11	Inadequate provision of fund for entrepreneurial research	90	2.77	1.18	Agreed
12	Lack of fund to carry out practical works for students	90	3.00	1.04	Agreed
13	Poor funds to carry out day to day entrepreneurship activities	90	2.98	1.07	Agreed
14	Gross lack of instructional materials for teaching entrepreneurship education	90	3.09	1.02	Agreed
15	Most of the entrepreneurship lecturers are borrowed from other discipline and are not qualified to teach the course	90	2.93	1.07	Agreed
16	There is gross lack of entrepreneurship teaching staff	90	2.97	1.09	Agreed
17	The teaching staff to the course are not well equipped with the practical aspect of teaching it	90	2.72	1.07	Agreed
18	There are no regular visits to companies and factories to acquire on the spot experience	90	3.06	.94	Agreed
19	Field trip lessons are skipped due to lack of time	90	3.01	1.20	Agreed
20	Lectures on entrepreneurship education receive equal amount of time like all other courses.	90	3.03	1.11	Agreed
Cluster Mean			29.56		
Mean of Item Means			2.956		

A look at table 2 shows the mean response of lecturers on management challenges of entrepreneurship education for sustainability of universities in Imo State, Nigeria. The result revealed that all the items, agreed having recorded mean scores above the criterion mean of 2.50. A look at the standard deviations proved they are far away from the mean and also that scores in the distribution are close to each other. It was also indicated that the mean of item mean is 2.956 showing that some challenges are facing the management of entrepreneurship education for sustainability of universities in Imo State, Nigeria. Some of these challenges are: inadequate provision of fund for entrepreneurial research, lack of fund to carry out practical works for students, the teaching staff to the course are not well equipped with the practical aspect of teaching it and there are no regular visits to companies and factories to acquire on the spot experience.

Hypothesis 1

Table 3: Sample Size (n), Summation ($\sum X$), Mean ($\bar{X}$), Standard Deviation (S), and one sample t-test statistics of significant difference between observed and expected means

n	$\bar{X}$	μ	S	S.E	df	t _{cal}	t _{tab.}	Decision
90	29.72	25	3.031	0.32	89	14.69	1.645	Ho Rejected

In table 3, further analysis using inferential statistics of one sample t-test revealed that the t-calculated of 14.69 is greater than the t-tabulated of 1.645. Thus, indicating that the null hypothesis be rejected and uphold the alternative hypothesis, hence, the mean score of lecturers in management tasks of entrepreneurship education for sustainability of universities in Imo State, Nigeria is significantly greater than 25. This implied that the management tasks of entrepreneurship education for sustainability of universities in Imo State, Nigeria are practiced above average.

Hypothesis 2

Table 4: Sample Size (n), Summation ($\sum X$), Mean ($\bar{X}$), Standard Deviation (S), and one sample t-test statistics of significant difference between observed and expected means

n	$\bar{X}$	μ	S	S.E	df	t _{cal}	t _{tab.}	Decision
90	29.56	25	3.05	0.32	89	14.10	1.645	Ho Rejected

In table 4, further analysis using inferential statistic of one sample t-test revealed that the t-calculated of 14.10 is greater than the t-tabulated of 1.645. Thus, indicating that the null hypothesis be rejected and upholding the alternative hypothesis, hence, the mean score of lecturers in management challenges of entrepreneurship education for sustainability of universities in Imo State, Nigeria is significantly greater than 25. This implied that the management challenges of entrepreneurship education for sustainability of universities in Imo State, Nigeria are really rated above average.

6. Discussion of Findings

It was found in this study that directors of entrepreneurship education are doing their tasks in the management of entrepreneurship education for sustainability of universities in Imo State, Nigeria. Some of the task areas they are performing are in assigning qualified lecturers for the teaching of various entrepreneurship education courses, providing orientation programmes for lecturers to create awareness on the need for entrepreneurship education, ensuring that modern information technology facilities for information gathering and dissemination are provided and ensuring that programmes are well articulated to help students explore different possibilities. The inference confirmed that the mean score of lecturers in management tasks of entrepreneurship education for sustainability of universities in Imo State, Nigeria is significantly greater than 25. This implied that the management tasks of entrepreneurship education for sustainability of universities in Imo State, Nigeria are practiced above average. In consonance with this finding, Asiyai (2009) found that the roles of school administrators in effective management of entrepreneurship education included provision of training on entrepreneurship education for teachers. Also, Uche and Adesope (2009) findings revealed that workshops and seminars are to be conducted for all faculties and at Academic Staff Union of Universities (ASUU) level to expose the lecturers to the concept of entrepreneurship and what their roles are in the implementation of entrepreneurship education in the university. Asiyai (2009) revealed the roles of school administrators in effective management of entrepreneurship education to include soliciting for improved funding of the programme through collaboration with Non Governmental Organizations (NGOs), Community Based Organizations (CBOs), and external agencies, improved monitoring and evaluation of the programme.

It was also found that some challenges are facing the management of entrepreneurship education for sustainability of universities in Imo State, Nigeria. Some of these challenges are inadequate provision of fund for entrepreneurial research, lack of fund to carry out practical works for students, the teaching staff for the courses are not well equipped with the practical aspect of teaching them and there are no regular visits to companies and factories to acquire on the spot experience. The inference confirmed that the mean score of lecturers in management challenges of entrepreneurship education for sustainability of universities in Imo State, Nigeria is significantly greater than 25. This implied that the management challenges of entrepreneurship education for sustainability of universities in Imo State, Nigeria are really rated above average. In line with this finding, Onye and Anyaogu (2014) revealed that inadequate provision of fund for entrepreneurial research, lack of fund to carry out practical works for students, inadequate funds to carry out day to day entrepreneurship activities and inadequate budgetary provisions challenge the implementation of the programme. Similarly, Obioma (2014) found among others that the level of funding entrepreneurship education curriculum in Universities located in Imo State was too low and this hindered the realization of its objectives. Also, Anaele, Adelakun, Dem and Barfa (2014) found out that

poor state of infrastructure posed challenge to entrepreneurship education in Nigerian schools. Also, Onye and Anyaogu (2014) found out that lack of teaching staff poses a challenge to the implementation of the programme. Congruently, Oku (2012) study identified that inadequate number of lecturers to teach entrepreneurship education in terms of quantity and quality is among some of the challenges facing the effective management of entrepreneurship education in Nigerian universities.

7. Conclusion

Based on the result of this study, the researcher concluded that directors of entrepreneurship education are doing their tasks in the management of entrepreneurship education for sustainability of universities in Imo State, Nigeria. However, some challenges are facing the management of entrepreneurship education for sustainability of universities in the state.

7.1 Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations were made:

1. The state and federal government should endeavour to provide adequate fund and capacity building for the administration of entrepreneurship education in Universities.
2. Training facilities with practical works should be made available by the University administrators and government.
3. The federal and state university vice chancellors with their directors in the entrepreneurship centers should involve the industrial sectors such as Breweries, Bakery and Water Packaging factories in the entrepreneurial training of university undergraduates.

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